

ARTERIAL STIFFNESS INDEX BETA AND CARDIO-ANKLE VASCULAR INDEX INHERENTLY DEPEND ON BLOOD PRESSURE, BUT CAN BE READILY CORRECTED

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1 ABSTRACT

2 **Objectives:** Arterial stiffness index β and cardio-ankle vascular index (CAVI) are
 3 widely accepted to quantify the intrinsic exponent (β_0) of the BP-diameter
 4 relationship. CAVI and β assume an exponential relationship between pressure (P)
 5 and diameter (d). We aim (1) to demonstrate that, under this assumption, β and CAVI
 6 as currently implemented are inherently BP-dependent; and (2) to provide corrected,
 7 BP-independent forms of CAVI and β .

8 **Methods and results:** In $P = P_{\text{ref}} e^{\beta_0 \left(\frac{d}{d_{\text{ref}}} - 1 \right)}$, usually reference pressure (P_{ref}) and
 9 reference diameter (d_{ref}) are substituted with diastolic BP and diameter to
 10 accommodate measurements. Consequently, the resulting exponent is not equal to
 11 the pressure-independent β_0 . CAVI does not only suffer from this "reference
 12 pressure" effect, but also from the approximation of $\frac{dP}{dd}$.

13 For example, assuming $\beta_0=7$, an increase of systolic/diastolic BP from 110/70 to
 14 170/120 mmHg increased β by 8.1% and CAVI by 14.3%. We derived corrected
 15 forms of β and of CAVI (CAVI₀) that indeed did not change with BP and represent the
 16 pressure-independent β_0 .

17 To substantiate the BP effect on CAVI in a typical follow-up study, we realistically
 18 simulated patients ($n=161$) before and following BP-lowering "treatment" (assuming
 19 no follow-up change in intrinsic β_0 and therefore in actual P - d relationship). Lowering
 20 BP from $160 \pm 14 / 111 \pm 11$ to $120 \pm 15 / 79 \pm 11$ mmHg ($p < 0.001$) resulted in a significant
 21 CAVI decrease (8.1 ± 2.0 to 7.7 ± 2.1 , $p = 0.008$); CAVI₀ did not change (9.8 ± 2.4 and
 22 9.9 ± 2.6 , $p = 0.499$).

23 **Conclusions:** β and CAVI as currently implemented are inherently BP-dependent,
 24 potentially leading to erroneous conclusions in arterial stiffness trials. BP-
 25 independent forms are presented to readily overcome this problem.

26 **Keywords:** arterial stiffness, arteriosclerosis, carotid compliance, pulse wave
 27 velocity, hypertension, blood pressure correction

28

29 INTRODUCTION

30 Arterial stiffness, as assessed by pulse wave velocity (PWV), is an important
31 independent predictor for cardiovascular disease. PWV, however, is known to
32 depend intrinsically on arterial blood pressure [1, 2]. This blood pressure dependence
33 has led to the search for blood pressure-independent measures of arterial stiffness.

34 As shown by Hayashi et al. [3], the relationship between arterial pressure and
35 diameter can be described by an exponential function in the physiological range (Fig.
36 1A). Throughout the present paper, this exponential relationship between arterial
37 pressure and diameter with pressure-independent exponent β_0 , is assumed as a
38 "ground truth" on which all other derivations are based. Of note, this paper has no
39 intention to prove the validity of this basic assumption.

40 Kawasaki et al. [4] proposed a clinically usable stiffness index β that is based on the
41 exponential relationship as demonstrated by Hayashi et al. [3]. In the present paper,
42 we will demonstrate that β is only an approximation of β_0 , and that β is in fact
43 pressure-dependent.

44 Cardio-ankle vascular index (CAVI) is being increasingly used in small and large
45 population studies [5], and is advocated as a pressure-independent index of arterial
46 stiffness [6]. CAVI is closely related to stiffness index β , and is also an approximation
47 of the exponent of the pressure-diameter relationship. Whereas β is used for local
48 characterisation of small artery segments, CAVI is derived as a summary measure
49 for the heart-to-ankle arterial trajectory. CAVI is obtained by measuring PWV and
50 converting it to an index using the Bramwell-Hill equation [1].

51 In the present paper, we will:

- 52 1. Show that β , as commonly calculated in biomedical literature, is not equal to
53 the actual, intrinsic stiffness index of the pressure-diameter relationship (β_0),
54 but instead varies with blood pressure.
- 55 2. Show that the blood pressure dependence of β can be corrected for, yielding a
56 formula to obtain the true, intrinsic stiffness index β_0 from the same
57 measurements.
- 58 3. Show that CAVI, which essentially is a form of stiffness index β , is also blood
59 pressure-dependent.
- 60 4. Show that a straightforward modification of the formula for calculating CAVI
61 yields a pressure-independent version, i.e. CAVI₀.

- 62 5. Illustrate the scientific and clinical relevance of our analysis and proposed
63 corrected β_0 and $CAVI_0$ formulas.

64 **METHODS**65 **Behaviour of the arterial wall: intrinsic stiffness index beta**

66 Hayashi et al. [3] showed experimentally that, in the physiological blood pressure
67 range, arterial pressure (P) and diameter (d) relate exponentially:

$$68 \quad P = P_{\text{ref}} e^{\beta_0 \left(\frac{d}{d_{\text{ref}}} - 1 \right)}. \quad (1)$$

69 Throughout this paper, this equation serves as our "ground truth". β_0 in this
70 relationship is an intrinsic, pressure-independent measure of arterial stiffness. Note
71 the use of P_{ref} (a "reference", or "standard" pressure) in this equation. d_{ref} is the
72 diameter corresponding to the reference pressure. Fig. 1A shows three pressure-
73 diameter relationships obtained using Eq. 1 at $\beta_0 = 7, 10, \text{ and } 15$. Each curve
74 corresponds to one β_0 value. $P_{\text{ref}} = 100$ mmHg was used throughout the present
75 study [3].

76 **Assessment of arterial wall mechanics: measured stiffness index beta**

77 Stiffness index β as commonly reported is calculated using a slightly different
78 equation than Eq. 1:

$$79 \quad P_s = P_d e^{\beta \left(\frac{d_s}{d_d} - 1 \right)}, \quad (2)$$

80 in which P_s , d_s , P_d , and d_d denote systolic and diastolic pressures and diameters,
81 respectively. Note the following differences between Eq. 1 and 2: a) reference
82 pressure and diameter have been changed to diastolic pressure and diameter; b)
83 instantaneous, variable pressure has been changed to systolic pressure; and c)
84 intrinsic stiffness index β_0 has been changed to measured stiffness β .

85 Eq. 2 can be rearranged to obtain the commonly-used expression for β :

$$86 \quad \beta = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\frac{d_s}{d_d} - 1}. \quad (3)$$

87 If this equation is used to quantify β in an exponentially-distending wall (Eq. 1) with a
 88 given $\beta_0 = 7$ and $P_{\text{ref}} = 100$ mmHg, calculated β 's will be dependent on the pressure
 89 ranges (Fig. 1B). This can be understood as follows.

90 **Pressure dependence of measured stiffness index β**

91 Suppose that two pressure-diameter points are measured on the intrinsic pressure-
 92 diameter relationship (Eq. 1): a systolic (P_s, d_s) and a diastolic (P_d, d_d) point. From Eq.
 93 3 and rearranging the result (see supplemental digital content 1 (SDC)), we obtain

$$94 \quad \beta = \beta_0 + \ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right). \quad (4)$$

95 This equation shows that β , the measured stiffness index, differs from the intrinsic
 96 stiffness index β_0 , by an amount of $\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right)$. This also implies that we can readily
 97 obtain the intrinsic, pressure-independent stiffness index β_0 by rearranging Eq. 4:

$$98 \quad \beta_0 = \beta - \ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right). \quad (5)$$

99 Note that if P_d is equal to P_{ref} , $\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right) = 0$ and β_0 equals β . However, in general, this
 100 is not the case.

101 Substituting the initial expression for β (Eq. 3) into Eq. 5 yields

$$102 \quad \beta_0 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\frac{d_s}{d_d} - 1} - \ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right), \quad (6)$$

103 which is a formulation that can be used to obtain the intrinsic, pressure-independent
 104 stiffness index β_0 from measured systolic and diastolic pressures and diameters.

105 **The value of P_{ref}**

106 The previous sections demonstrate that the pressure (either P_d or P_{ref}) that is used to
 107 multiply the exponential function influences the value of β or β_0 that is obtained. It is
 108 important to realise that a value of β_0 *corresponds to* a P_{ref} value. Therefore, one
 109 should choose one, *fixed* P_{ref} value for *all* subjects in a study, in order to be able to
 110 compare the β_0 values among these subjects. The numerical value of P_{ref} that is

111 chosen is a matter of standardisation or consensus. P_{ref} does *not* represent a
 112 physiological pressure. Different values of P_{ref} (and the corresponding d_{ref}) lead to
 113 different values of β_0 . However, the P - d curves that are described using these
 114 different combinations of $P_{\text{ref}}/d_{\text{ref}}/\beta_0$ perfectly and analytically overlap. Therefore, P_{ref}
 115 values should be taken *equal* between studies (irrespective of the patient cohort
 116 studied), if β_0 -values are to be compared between those studies. Arbitrarily, in the
 117 present study, we have chosen $P_{\text{ref}} = 100$ mmHg.

118 **Cardio-ankle vascular index (CAVI)**

119 Stiffness index β , (Eq. 3), which is a function of pressures (P_d and P_s) and diameters
 120 (d_d and d_s), can also be expressed as a function of pressures and PWV. This is
 121 accomplished by combining Eq. 3 with a simplified version of the Bramwell-Hill
 122 equation (SDC Eq. S10) [1]. When PWV in this equation is determined from the
 123 heart-to-ankle arterial bed, the resulting quantity (in fact a β index) is termed cardio-
 124 vascular index (CAVI):

$$125 \quad \text{CAVI} = \ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right) \cdot \frac{\text{PWV}^2 \cdot 2\rho}{P_s - P_d} \quad (7)$$

126 PWV from the heart to the ankle is obtained using a combination of the
 127 phonocardiogram, electrocardiogram, and a brachial and ankle cuff [6].

128 For the same reasons outlined in the previous section (the use of diastolic blood
 129 pressure instead of a reference blood pressure), CAVI is pressure-dependent.
 130 However, CAVI also depends on blood pressure for another reason, as explained
 131 below.

132 The derivation of CAVI [6] is based on a simplified version of the Bramwell-Hill
 133 equation (Fig. 2B), in which the derivative of pressure to diameter ($\frac{dP}{dd}$) is replaced by
 134 a linear approximation over the diastolic-to-systolic pressure range. This
 135 approximation introduces an error in the obtained CAVI value. The magnitude of this
 136 error can be quantified using the true PWV, i.e., the PWV based on the true $\frac{dP}{dd}$ in the
 137 diastolic point (SDC Eq. S11). Using this PWV to calculate CAVI by means of Eq. 7
 138 yields:

139
$$\text{CAVI} = \left(\beta_0 + \ln \left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}} \right) \right) \cdot \ln \left(\frac{P_s}{P_d} \right) \cdot \frac{P_d}{P_s - P_d} . \quad (8)$$

140 The extra terms beside β_0 in the right hand side of this equation indicate the
141 pressure dependence of CAVI (Fig. 2C).

142 **Finding a pressure-independent CAVI**

143 A pressure-independent CAVI formula should provide an index equivalent to the
144 intrinsic stiffness index β_0 . Such an index can be derived by squaring and
145 rearranging the relationship between true PWV (obtained from the exact, analytic
146 derivative of the P - d relationship) and β_0 (SDC Eq. S13):

147
$$\text{CAVI}_0 = \beta_0 = \frac{\text{PWV}^2 \cdot 2\rho}{P_d} - \ln \left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}} \right) . \quad (9)$$

148 This equation can be used to obtain the pressure independent CAVI_0 from PWV, ρ ,
149 and P_d (Fig. 2D).

150 **Simulations**

151 *Residual blood pressure dependence of stiffness index β and CAVI*

152 In order to quantify the blood pressure dependence of stiffness index β , we
153 calculated β (Eq. 4) at two clearly distinct blood pressure ranges (normotensive
154 110/70 mmHg systolic/diastolic BP (SBP/DBP) and hypertensive 170/120 mmHg). We
155 did so for two values of intrinsic stiffness: $\beta_0 = 7$ and $\beta_0 = 15$, corresponding to a
156 normal young subject and an older subject with a stiffened artery, respectively. The
157 reference diameter (d_{ref}) was kept constant at 20 mm. The quantitative effect of
158 blood pressure on CAVI was determined for the same blood pressure ranges and β_0
159 values (Eq. 8).

160 *Blood pressure dependence of CAVI in a simulated population study*

161 In order to gain insight into the magnitude of the blood pressure dependence of CAVI
162 and how this could affect a typical study's results, we computer-simulated a blood
163 pressure-lowering treatment in a population with an average intrinsic stiffness $\beta_0 =$

164 10. For a detailed description of the protocol for data generation and randomisation,
165 we refer the reader to the SDC.

166 In short, we simulated a baseline and a follow-up measurement between which blood
167 pressure decreased on average from about 160/110 (SBP/DBP) to about 120/80
168 mmHg. Importantly, we assumed wall behaviour to remain unchanged. That is, with
169 the blood pressure change for each subject, the exponential P - d relationship (Eq. 1)
170 and, hence, β_0 remained unchanged. DBP, SBP, and PWV values before and
171 following “treatment” were drawn from normal distributions, simulating biological
172 variation. Subsequently, measurements were simulated by adding normally-
173 distributed measurement noise. CAVI and $CAVI_0$ were calculated from these
174 simulated measurements.

175 Using the simulated population data, we calculated the sample size at which, for a
176 power of 80% and $\alpha = 0.05$, the blood pressure lowering would lead to a statistically
177 significant change in CAVI. Subsequently, we simulated a study in the number of
178 subjects obtained from the sample size calculation to illustrate a typical study's
179 results.

180

181 RESULTS

182 Residual blood pressure dependence of stiffness index β and CAVI

183 Fig. 1B shows the quantitative effect of blood pressure on stiffness index β . With
184 increasing blood pressure from 110/70 mmHg to 170/120 mmHg (SBP/DBP), β
185 increased by 8.1% (from 6.6 to 7.2) in a young individual's artery with $\beta_0=7$. In an
186 older individual's artery with $\beta_0=15$, β increased by 3.7% (from 14.6 to 15.2).

187 Pressure dependence of β was markedly smaller than that of PWV. PWV changed to
188 a much larger extent with blood pressure; from 5.4 to 7.4 m/s in the young artery
189 (36% change) and from 8.1 to 10.8 m/s in the older artery (33% change). Stiffness
190 index β as determined using the corrected equation (Eq. 6, yielding β_0) was
191 independent of pressure (Fig. 1C).

192 Fig. 2C shows the quantitative effect of blood pressure on CAVI. With increasing
193 blood pressure from 110/70 mmHg to 170/120 mmHg (SBP/DBP), CAVI increased
194 from 5.3 to 6.0 (14.3% increase) in a young individual and from 11.6 to 12.7 (9.6%
195 change) in an older individual. Furthermore, using the standard CAVI formula leads
196 to much lower values for β than the actual, intrinsic β_0 s of 7 and 15.

197 CAVI as determined using the corrected equation (Eq. 9, yielding $CAVI_0$) was
198 independent of pressure (Fig. 2D).

199 Fig. 3 shows how stiffness index β (A) and CAVI (B) depend on diastolic and systolic
200 blood pressures. Comparing Figs. 3A and 3B, one sees that (i) β only depends on
201 DBP, whereas CAVI depends on DBP and SBP; and that (ii) the blood pressure
202 dependence of CAVI is much larger than that of β (viz., compare the different colour
203 scales of panes A and B). The larger blood pressure dependence of CAVI is caused
204 by the use of an approximated derivative in the CAVI formula (Fig. 2B), in addition to
205 the "reference pressure" effect that affects both β and CAVI.

206 **Simulated impact of the blood pressure dependence of CAVI in a population**
207 **study**

208 For our simulated population, we determined that a sample size of 161 subjects
209 would give an 80% chance of finding a statistically significant difference in CAVI due
210 to blood pressure lowering. Table 1 shows the results of a simulated set of
211 measurements in 161 subjects. Values throughout are expressed as mean \pm standard
212 deviation.

213 For the lowering of systolic blood pressure from 160 ± 14 mmHg to 120 ± 15 mmHg
214 ($p < 0.001$) and diastolic blood pressure from 110 ± 11 mmHg to 79 ± 11 mmHg
215 ($p < 0.001$), PWV significantly decreased from 8.2 ± 1.1 to 6.9 ± 1.0 m/s ($p < 0.001$).
216 CAVI as calculated from the standard equation (Eq. 7; CAVI) significantly decreased
217 from 8.1 ± 2.0 to 7.7 ± 2.1 ($p = 0.008$) with lowering blood pressure, as expected for
218 the sample size.

219 The corrected CAVI as proposed and calculated from Eq. 9 (CAVI₀) showed no
220 change with blood pressure ($p = 0.499$).

221

222 DISCUSSION

223 CAVI and β assume an exponential relationship between pressure and diameter. In
 224 this study, we have demonstrated that, under this assumption and contrary to the
 225 often made claim [6], stiffness index β and CAVI are BP-dependent. This confirms
 226 findings by Lim et al. [7], who showed a BP dependence of CAVI in an experimental
 227 setting. However, the blood pressure dependence of other artery stiffness
 228 parameters, such as PWV [2], is greater than that of β and CAVI.

229 Using CAVI under the assumption of it being fully blood pressure independent may
 230 confound conclusions, especially in large population studies investigating relatively
 231 small changes in CAVI. For example, several studies have reported that arterial
 232 stiffness, as measured with CAVI, decreases with blood pressure-lowering
 233 medication [5, 8]. However, our simulations show that even in a study with relatively
 234 few participants ($n = 161$) where intrinsic wall parameters (β_0) were explicitly kept
 235 constant, the blood pressure effect on CAVI may emerge as statistically significant.

236 In our simulation study, the BP effect on PWV (1.3 m/s) is much larger than the
 237 within-subject standard deviation of 0.5 m/s [9]. The BP-induced change of CAVI of
 238 0.4 in our simulation study is of the same order as the CAVI within-subject standard
 239 deviation of 0.5 [10]. This comparison (i) underlines the much smaller BP
 240 dependence of CAVI when compared to PWV and (ii) emphasises that CAVI as
 241 usually implemented may lead to erroneous conclusions.

242 As mentioned in the introduction, Kawasaki et al. previously derived β from β_0 [4, 11].
 243 In their derivation, they correctly mentioned that clinically, it is difficult to measure
 244 diameter at a standard pressure of e.g., 100 mmHg. After this notice, they simplified
 245 Eq. 1 to Eq. 2, thereby neglecting the underlying blood pressure dependence
 246 emerging from substituting *diastolic* blood pressure and *diastolic* diameter for P_{ref} and
 247 d_{ref} in Eq. 1.

248 Note that CAVI as reported by the VaSera device by Fukuda Denshi, Co. LTD
 249 (CAVI_{VS}) is a scaled version of CAVI as used in this paper: $\text{CAVI}_{\text{VS}} = a \cdot \text{CAVI} + b$ [6].
 250 The constants a and b are considered proprietary information by the company and
 251 therefore are not publically available. However, as a and b constants, the BP
 252 dependence of CAVI is equally applicable to CAVI_{VS} .

253 The present study relies on the assumption that the *in vivo* arterial wall pressure-
254 diameter relationship is exponential. The underlying arterial wall mechanics of the
255 exponential behaviour are complex. At lower pressures, mainly elastin bears the
256 load, whereas at higher pressures, this load bearing is gradually shifted to collagen
257 [12, 13]. This shift leads to the typical form of the full *P-d* relationship, which, starting
258 from $P=0$ first shows an *increase* in compliance, then has a maximum, and
259 subsequently decreases with increasing pressure [14]. The maximum compliance,
260 corresponding to an inflection point in the *P-d* relationship, occurs at a pressure of
261 around 45 mmHg in individuals aged 30 years. With increasing age, the pressure at
262 which the maximum compliance occurs decreases and becomes 0 mmHg at the age
263 of 80 [15]. If this full *P-d* relationship with an inflection point is to be described, a
264 single-exponential *P-d* relationship is clearly insufficient; an arctangent-type model
265 may be more suitable in this case [14].

266 Because young subjects have an inflection point at relatively high pressures of ≈ 45
267 mmHg, the assumption of a single-exponential relationship may not hold when they
268 are hypotensive. In this case, their low diastolic blood pressures may be close to their
269 inflection point. However, in all other subjects, physiological blood pressures are
270 normally well above the inflection point. Therefore, a single-exponential relationship
271 provides an appropriate approximation of the true *P-d* relationship.

272 The exponential shape of the *P-d* relationship as shown *in vitro* by Hayashi et al. [3]
273 was confirmed *in vivo* in humans by Stefanadis et al. [16]. They reported that "the
274 pressure-diameter data fitted excellently to the monoexponential function $P=bx e^{a \cdot D}$,
275 ($r=.97$ to $.99$, $p<.001$), ..." in the human aorta, both in normotensive and hypertensive
276 subjects. Later studies by these investigators again confirmed this finding [17, 18].

277 The choice of an exponential *P-d* relationship has a pragmatic reason. Models that
278 are more complicated than the single-exponential model cannot be uniquely
279 parameterised using a set of two pressures (systolic and diastolic) and two diameters
280 or a PWV. This limits their use to very specific research studies in which the full
281 pressure-diameter relationship is measured, or in which more than two *P-d* points are
282 measured (e.g., by adding an additional dicrotic notch point [19]). In our opinion, this
283 limitation, together with the *in vivo* validations by Stefanadis et al. [16], makes a

284 strong case for using an exponential model to characterise *in vivo* arterial *P-d*
285 relationships.

286 **Conclusion**

287 CAVI and stiffness index β rely on the assumption of an exponential relationship
288 between pressure and diameter. In this paper we have shown that, under this
289 assumption, stiffness index β and CAVI as commonly implemented, depend on blood
290 pressure. This dependence can potentially lead to erroneous conclusions in studies
291 that use β and CAVI to estimate changes in stiffness of the artery wall. We have
292 presented corrected stiffness indices, β_0 and $CAVI_0$, that readily overcome this
293 problem.

294 **Perspectives**

295 The findings presented in this manuscript have direct implications for all studies that
296 incorporate β and/or CAVI measurements. We have shown that due care should be
297 taken in interpreting β and CAVI as strictly pressure-independent measures of arterial
298 stiffness. In a moderately-sized study, a blood pressure decrease from a
299 hypertensive to a normotensive range may lead to a significant decrease in CAVI as
300 calculated from the standard equation, merely due to the change in blood pressure.
301 $CAVI_0$ as derived in the present study, does not exhibit this pressure dependence.
302 Our new formulations (β_0 and $CAVI_0$) allow even retrospective data analysis for
303 improved interpretation of arterial stiffness trials. Recently, we have shown that the
304 degree of BP dependence of PWV is clinically relevant [2], and that the BP
305 dependence is apparent from the PWV reference values [20]. Based on the
306 reference values for PWV, and considering the approach proposed in the present
307 paper, pressure-independent reference values for $\beta_0/CAVI_0$ could be obtained.

308

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311

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379 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

380 **Figure 1.** Pressure dependence of stiffness index beta (β). A: Intrinsic relationship
 381 between arterial pressure and diameter (Eq. 1). Hayashi et al. showed that in the
 382 physiological pressure range, this relationship is exponential [3]. The exponential
 383 nature of this relationship is assumed as a "ground truth" in this paper, serving as the
 384 basis for all other derivations. Pressure ranges (systolic/diastolic blood pressure)
 385 indicated in this panel are used for calculating stiffness parameters in panels B and
 386 C. $P_{\text{ref}} = 100$ mmHg is a reference pressure (Eq. 1). d_{ref} is the diameter
 387 corresponding to the reference pressure. d_{ref} is kept fixed at 20 mm to illustrate
 388 solely the effect of a change in β_0 on the pressure-diameter relationship. B:
 389 Measured stiffness index beta β as computed from systolic and diastolic pressures
 390 (P_s, P_d) and diameters (d_s, d_d) on panel A's curves, is blood pressure-dependent.
 391 Because the pressure dependence of β can be shown to exist mathematically (Eq.
 392 4), β can be corrected using $\ln(P_d/P_{\text{ref}})$, obtaining the intrinsic, pressure-independent
 393 stiffness index beta (β_0 , panel C). P_{ref} and d_{ref} , reference blood pressure and
 394 diameter corresponding to Eq. 1.

395 **Figure 2.** Pressure dependence of cardio-ankle vascular index (CAVI). A: Intrinsic P -
 396 d relations (Eq. 1) and pressure ranges (systolic/diastolic blood pressure) used for
 397 calculating CAVI in panels C and D. $P_{\text{ref}} = 100$ mmHg and $d_{\text{ref}} = 20$ mm. B: As CAVI
 398 is essentially a form of stiffness index beta, the pressure dependence as shown in
 399 Fig. 1 also holds for CAVI. In CAVI, however, there is a second source of pressure
 400 dependence, which arises as follows. In the normal CAVI formula, an approximation
 401 of the Bramwell-Hill equation is used, effectively substituting $\frac{dP}{dd}$ with $\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta d}$. Therefore, if
 402 CAVI is determined using measured PWV and the standard equation (Eq. 7) [6],
 403 CAVI shows a blood pressure dependence (panel C). D: As CAVI assumes an
 404 exponential pressure-diameter relationship (Eq. 1), one can analytically determine
 405 the true $\frac{dP}{dd}$. By using this analytic expression, one can find a pressure-independent
 406 formulation of CAVI (CAVI_0). Note the presence of the $\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right)$ term, which is also
 407 present in the corrected form of stiffness index beta (Eq. 6 and Fig. 1C).

408 **Figure 3.** Dependence of stiffness index β and CAVI on diastolic and systolic blood
 409 pressures (DBP and SBP). A: β depends on DBP due to the "reference point" effect

410 (cf. the difference between Eqs. 1 and 2). B: The "reference point" effect also
411 influences CAVI, causing a dependence of CAVI on DBP. CAVI is additionally blood
412 pressure-dependent due to the use of an approximated derivative in the Bramwell-Hill
413 equation (Fig. 2B), also introducing a dependence on SBP. Plots were generated for
414 $P_{\text{ref}} = 100$ mmHg and $\beta_0 = 7$ (see text).

415 **TABLES**416 **Table 1.** Uncorrected cardio-ankle vascular index (CAVI) leads to misinterpretation.

parameter	unit	baseline	follow-up	<i>p</i>
SBP	mmHg	161 ± 14	120 ± 15	<0.001
DBP	mmHg	111 ± 11	79 ± 11	<0.001
PWV	m/s	8.2 ± 1.1	6.9 ± 1.0	<0.001
CAVI	-	8.1 ± 2.0	7.7 ± 2.1	0.008
CAVI ₀	-	9.8 ± 2.4	9.9 ± 2.6	0.499

417 Pressure dependence of CAVI in a simulated data set ($n = 161$). Values denote
418 mean \pm standard deviation. SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood
419 pressure; PWV, pulse wave velocity; CAVI, standard, pressure-dependent cardio-
420 ankle vascular index (Eq. 7); CAVI₀, corrected, pressure-independent cardio-ankle
421 vascular index (Eq. 9); p , p -value of two-sided paired t-test comparing baseline to
422 follow-up values. Intrinsic stiffness index β_0 was 9.8 ± 1.9 , and was equal at baseline
423 and follow-up.

424 FIGURES

425

426 **Figure 1.** Pressure dependence of stiffness index beta (β). A: Intrinsic relationship
 427 between arterial pressure and diameter (Eq. 1). Hayashi et al. showed that in the
 428 physiological pressure range, this relationship is exponential [3]. The exponential
 429 nature of this relationship is assumed as a "ground truth" in this paper, serving as the
 430 basis for all other derivations. Pressure ranges (systolic/diastolic blood pressure)
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 433 corresponding to the reference pressure. d_{ref} is kept fixed at 20 mm to illustrate
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 436 (P_s , P_d) and diameters (d_s , d_d) on panel A's curves, is blood pressure-dependent.
 437 Because the pressure dependence of β can be shown to exist mathematically (Eq.
 438 4), β can be corrected using $\ln(P_d/P_{ref})$, obtaining the intrinsic, pressure-independent
 439 stiffness index beta (β_0 , panel C). P_{ref} and d_{ref} , reference blood pressure and
 440 diameter corresponding to Eq. 1.

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443 **Figure 2.** Pressure dependence of cardio-ankle vascular index (CAVI). A: Intrinsic P -
 444 d relations (Eq. 1) and pressure ranges (systolic/diastolic blood pressure) used for
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